

GS 80 "WATER SHAFT" WATER LEVEL MEASUREMENT

SHAFT A" From top edge Bedrock (causeway surface) to bottom rung of ladder showing above sand fill. 9.90 m.

9.90 level to top of Shaft B 1.62
(w/ line level taken over) 9.90
1.62
11.52

Top edge of Shaft B to bottom arbitrary point just above "floor" 12.20 11.52
12.20
23.72

To top of Shaft C from arbitrary "12.20" point (Pipe at top of C) 1.35 1.35

Top of Shaft "C" to surface water 7.04 23.72
1.35
25.07
7.04
32.11

ELEVATION: POINT ON TOP SHAFT "A"

TOTAL DEPTH FROM POINT "A" AT TOP SHAFT "A"

500/2990 = 10.80 10.80 SIGHT → .68 $\frac{2}{3} \times 3.36$ 12.41
1.61 → 3.36 - .68 2.68
12.41 I.H. 2.68 15.09 I.H.

15.09 15.09 15.09 → .865 $\frac{2}{3} \times 3.43$ 15.09
1.51 60.5 57 → 3.73 $\frac{2}{3} \times 86.5$ 2.865
13.58 14.485 14.22 2.865 17.855 I.H.

17.855 17.855 17.855 → .25 3.76 17.855 21.365
2.59 2.57 1.85 7.87 → 3.76 - .25 3.51 3.17
15.365 15.285 16.005 16.985 3.51 21.365 I.H. 18.195

21.365 21.365 → .02 3.855 21.365 → .055 3.635
2.25 1.40 → 3.855 .02 3.835 25.20 I.H. 3.635
19.115 19.965 3.835 25.20 I.H. 3.635 3.58

25.20 → .03 3.465 28.78 → .02 3.71 32.215
3.58 → 3.465 .03 3.435 3.435 3.71 3.71 .02 3.69
28.78 I.H. 32.215 I.H. 3.69 35.905 I.H.

→ .085 3.875 35.905 39.695
→ 3.875 .085 3.79 1.58
3.79 39.695 38.115 ELEVATION

38.115 elevation top shaft "A"

- 32.11 Depth from top shaft "A" to water surface in shaft "C"

6.00

OR 5.995 = ELEVATION WATER SURFACE IN WATER SHAFT

ELEVATION WATER SURFACE IN SPHINX RUMP PASSAGE 26X180 = 6.17
- 5.995
175

38.115
- 11.52
26.585 ELEVATION TENTATIVE MEMBER 2 CONTACT IN WATER SHAFT

LES PAPIERS GANSON - FRANCE